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Transition-metal free highly selective aerobic oxidation of hindered 2-alkylindoles

[Morteza Shiri](#),^{*,a} Behnaz Farajpour^a, Zahra Bozorgpour-Savadjani^a, Suhas A. Shintre^b, Neil A. Koorbanally^b, Hendrik G. Kruger^c, Behrouz Notash^d

a Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Alzahra University, Vanak, Tehran 1993893973, Iran .

b School of Chemistry and Physics, University of KwaZulu-Natal (UKZN), Durban 4001, South Africa.

c Catalysis and Peptide Research Unit, School of Health Sciences, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Durban 4001, South Africa.

d Department of Chemistry, Shahid Beheshti University, G. C., Evin, Tehran 1983963113, Iran.

Abstract

A novel and easy access to highly complex 3-oxoindolin-2-ylidene derivatives from the exposure of Ugiadducts bearing an indolyl moiety in Cs₂CO₃/DMF to air is reported. This is the first example of aerobic oxidation of 2-alkylindoles to 3-oxoindolin-2-ylidenes. Some advantages of this method are the use of air as oxygen source, transition metal-free reagents and simple conditions, a multicomponent and one-pot process and highly regio- and stereoselective manner to trans-3-oxoindolin-2-ylidenes.

Keywords: Condensation, Indole, Aerobic oxidation, Basic media and aprotic solvent.